

An Open Source, Parallel, and Distributed Web-Based Probabilistic Risk Assessment Platform to Support Real Time Nuclear Power Plant Risk-Informed Operational Decisions

Milestone Report

Task 6: Verification and Documentation

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Executive Summary

This milestone report provides an overview of our approach to documenting OpenPRA, as well as the development of a verification platform that supports both OpenPRA and the broader research community.

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Disclaimer

The content of this report is largely a combination of various project outcomes, including conference papers, a master's thesis, and a Ph.D. dissertation.

Outcomes of the Project

The project contributes to the research environment in various ways, and the outcomes are listed below for reference. In addition to the listed outcomes, two journal papers are ready for submission, and one report covering the SAPHIRE post-processing engine is under review. Furthermore, North Carolina State University and Idaho National Laboratory have established a highly efficient collaborative environment.

1.1 Conference Papers

1. Benchmark Study of XFTA and SCRAM Fault Tree Solvers Using Synthetically Generated Fault Tree Models [1]
2. Methodology and Demonstration for Performance Analysis of a Probabilistic Risk Assessment Quantification Engine: SCRAM [2]
3. Method of Developing a SCRAM Parallel Engine for Efficient Quantification of Probabilistic Risk Assessment Models [3]
4. Introducing OpenPRA: A Web-Based Framework for Collaborative Probabilistic Risk Assessment [4]
5. Evaluating PRA Tools for Accurate and Efficient Quantifications: A Follow-up Benchmarking Study Including FTREX [5]
6. Introducing OpenPRA's Quantification Engine: Exploring Capabilities, Recognizing Limitations, and Charting the Path to Enhancement [6]
7. Enhancing the SAPHIRE Solve Engine: Initial Progress and Efforts [7]
8. Advancing SAPHIRE: Transitioning from Legacy to State-of-Art Excellence [8]
9. Towards a Deep-Learning Based Heuristic for Optimal Variable Ordering in Binary Decision Diagrams to Support Fault Tree Analysis [9]

1.2 Journal Papers

1. A Critical Look at the Need for Performing Multi-Hazard Probabilistic Risk Assessment for Nuclear Power Plants [10]

1.3 Reports

1. Refining Processing Engines from SAPHIRE: Initialization of Fault Tree/Event Tree Solver [11]

1.4 Master's Thesis

1. Benchmarking Study of Probabilistic Risk Assessment Tools Using Synthetically Generated Fault Tree Models: SAPHSOLVE, XFTA, and SCRAM [12]

1.5 Ph.D. Dissertation

1. Enhancement Methodology for Probabilistic Risk Assessment Tools through Optimization and Parallel Computing [13]

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
CD	Continuous Deployment
CI	Continuous Integration
CLI	Command Line Interface
DevOps	Development and Operations
HTML	Hypertext Markup Language
IT	Information Technology
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
NPP	Nuclear Power Plant
PWR	Pressurized Water Reactor
UI	User Interface
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
XML	Extensible Markup Language

1 Verification and Documentation

1.1 Overview of the Report

This report marks a significant milestone in the overall project. As a reminder, the project consists of five main tasks, which are outlined below. This milestone report presents the outcomes of the fifth task:

- Task 1: Literature review, benchmarking, and profiling of current PRA tools
- Task 2: Design and implementation
- Task 3: Testing and benchmarking for serial and parallel improvements
- Task 4: Application to real world PRA models
- Task 5: Verification and documentation

The remainder of the report is as follows:

1.2 Automated Documentation Generation

The documentation for the OpenPRA web app is organized into two main categories:

- documentation for future developers
- documentation for potential users or clients

Given the rapid evolution of web development stacks, it is crucial to provide clear documentation for the developer community. This ensures that developers can quickly grasp the core functionalities of OpenPRA's various components and methods, allowing them to focus on developing features or fix bugs of the app rather than spending time on going through source code. For users, who may want to use different parts of OpenPRA—such as the frontend, backend, distributed systems, or the engine—as standalone packages, the documentation provides guidance on how to interact with these components via Application Programming Interfaces (API)s. This way, the source code will be abstracted from the users and the users will still understand how to integrate the packages into their own projects. The documentation is designed with both developers and users in mind, ensuring consistency, facilitating collaboration, and aiding in the implementation of hot-fixes or quick fixes.

1.2.1 HTML Formatted Documentation

The front-end, back-end, and the distributed system are all written in TypeScript [14]. Initially, JSDoc [15] was used for documentation, but the project has since transitioned to TSDoc [16] for documenting these packages. Both JSDoc and TSDoc are standardized protocols for documentation of TypeScript codes. The scam-node engine and its wrapper methods, which are written in C++, use Doxygen-style [17] comments for documentation. In the front-end, TSDoc-style comments are placed either above component methods or within the methods themselves to explain the source code. For the backend and distributed system, comments are added above controller and service classes, as well as within individual methods. These comments typically describe the expected input parameters, their types, what they represent, and the type and description of the output. Additionally, inline comments are used to explain third-party methods and APIs used inside the source code or to serve as reminders for future development or fixes. Sometimes comments are added above tests to outline what functionality, and which part of the source code is being tested.

Figure 1. HTML-formatted documentation for the components of the distributed systems microservice.

Whenever the frontend, backend, distributed systems, or engine are compiled, the TSDoc and Doxygen-style comments are automatically converted into Hypertext Markup Language (HTML) documentation using command-line interface (CLI) commands from third-party libraries. These HTML pages can be accessed via specific Uniform Resource Locaters (URL)s, providing users with a high-level overview of the codebase without

requiring them to have an in-depth knowledge of the source code. For generating these automated HTML formatted documentation of the frontend, backend, distributed system, and engine – different libraries such as TypeDoc [18], Compodoc [19] and Doxygen are used. Figure 1 shows such a HTML-formatted documentation page generated by Compodoc for the distributed systems microservice.

1.2.2 Interactive API Documentation

OpenPRA users can interact with the backend and distributed system through the Swagger user interface (UI), a UI that follows the OpenAPI [20] specification. OpenAPI provides a set of rules for describing REST APIs, while Swagger is a collection of open-source tools built around the OpenAPI specification to help design, build, document, and consume REST APIs. Swagger goes through the OpenPRA source code and identifies the available endpoints defined in the controllers of the backend and distributed system packages. It also detects the type of operations associated with each endpoint (such as GET, POST, PUT/PATCH, DELETE, etc.). In addition to endpoints, Swagger captures the input parameters and output for each operation, and it can enforce authentication methods on specific endpoints. Furthermore, Swagger allows for the inclusion of additional metadata, such as titles, descriptions, tags, contact information, licenses, terms of use, and more. Figure 2 shows such an interactive API documentation for the distributed systems microservice. The responses from operations are returned in a combined format of an HTTP status code and a JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) body. This interactive process allows users to easily integrate the backend, distributed system, and scram-node engine into their own projects, enabling them to seamlessly send model data to the OpenPRA engine for quantification.

1.2.3 Documentation for DevOps

DevOps is a collaborative approach that integrates code development (Dev) and information technology (IT) operations (Ops) to streamline the entire software lifecycle—from coding and testing to deployment and maintenance. It emphasizes automation of testing, continuous integration (CI) of code, and continuous deployment (CD) of the app. In the OpenPRA codebase, each standalone package (frontend, backend, distributed system, databases, and scram-engine) includes its own set of instructions in the respective *readme.md* files. These instructions clearly outline how to install the necessary dependencies, compile the source files, spin up the individual packages or launch them together as the OpenPRA app, run tests, and enforce code formatting using linting rules. In addition to these manual processes, Docker files have been created to automate the entire setup, and documentation is provided on how to run these Docker files within containers. All the essential tools for development, testing, and automation are available for the developers as well as the users, along with detailed guidance on how to use them

effectively. Code snippets from the DevOps documentation have been provided in Appendix A in Section 3.1 at the end of the report.

The screenshot displays the Swagger UI for the 'OpenPRA Distributed Multi-Queue API' (version 0.0.1, OAS 3.0). The page title is 'OpenPRA Distributed Multi-Queue API' and the description is 'PRA quantification and task execution message-broker'. The license is 'AGPL-3.0-or-later'. The 'default' section lists the following endpoints:

- GET /api/job-types: Retrieves a list of job types
- GET /api/pending-jobs: Retrieves a list of pending jobs
- POST /api/create-job: Creates a new job
- POST /api/quantify/scram: Endpoint to create and queue a quantification job for SCRAM
- GET /api/quantify/scram: Controller method to handle GET requests for quantified reports at the "scram" endpoint
- POST /api/quantify/ftrex: Endpoint to create and queue a quantification job for the FTREX solver
- GET /api/quantify/ftrex: Controller method to handle GET requests for quantified reports at the "ftrex" endpoint
- POST /api/execute/tasks: Create a new execution task
- GET /api/execute/tasks: Endpoint to retrieve a list of executed tasks and their results

Figure 2. Interactive API documentation for the controller of distributed systems microservice.

1.3 Verification

Public repositories has been created to serve as a verification environment. It includes a variety of models that have already been quantified using either SAPH SOLVE [21] or SCRAM [22], enabling users to validate the results of their own quantification engines. Currently, the models are available in Open-PSA Extensible Markup Language (XML) [23] and SAPH SOLVE JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) [11] formats; however, efforts are ongoing to convert these models into additional formats. Additionally, more models are under development, particularly multi-hazard models, for further completeness.

Below is a summarized list of the current models available for verification purposes:

- Open-PSA XML models:
 - Converted generic Pressurized Water Reactor (PWR) full model, version 1.2
 - Various publicly available EDF models
 - SCRAM non-identified test models, some of which are actual models referenced in various publications [24], though their exact representation is not disclosed

- Synthetically generated fault tree models with basic events of both high and low probability
- SAPHSOLVE JSON models:
- ETH Boiling Water Reactor (BWR) model
- ETH PWR model
- Generic PWR model, version 1.2
- Synthetically generated fault tree models with basic events of low probability

The schema for both Open-PSA XML and SAPHSOLVE JSON formats is also available through the repository.

The ability to generate synthetic fault trees and actual models, such as the generic PWR, is a highly valuable contribution to the community. Given the difficulty in sharing actual nuclear power plant (NPP) models publicly, these representative models provide an important resource for testing quantification engines.

1.4 Conclusion and Alignment to Project Goals

Continuous improvement of software, such as OpenPRA in our case, requires detailed documentation and a diverse set of representative test cases for verification purposes. As a result of this task, we have established a well-documented implementation and a robust verification platform that benefits not only OpenPRA but also the broader research community. This platform will continue to be enhanced as development progresses.

2 References

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3 Appendices

3.1 Appendix A: Code Snippets from DevOps Documentation

The following code snippets provide instructions for running the OpenPRA app in a docker container with all the necessary dependencies:

```
1. # Docker Configuration
2.
3. The configuration is designed to build and deploy a full-stack application with `web-editor`,
`web-backend`, and a MongoDB database, along with a Mongo Express for database management during
development.
4.
5. ## Overview
6.
7. The Docker setup is divided into several components:
8.
9. - **Dockerfile**: Defines the multi-stage build process for creating Docker images for both the
frontend and backend services.
10. - **default.conf**: The Nginx configuration file for the frontend service, which serves the static
files and proxies requests.
11. - **docker-compose.yml**: A Docker Compose file for local development, setting up the MongoDB and
Mongo Express services.
12. - **stack.yml**: A Docker Stack deployment file for deploying the services using Docker Swarm,
with Traefik as a reverse proxy and load balancer.
13.
14. ## [Dockerfile](Dockerfile)
15.
16. The `Dockerfile` is a multi-stage build file that creates separate images for
17. the frontend and backend services.
18.
19. - **Base Image**: Built from `node:20.2.0-slim`, it installs necessary build tools and the NX
CLI.
20. - **Frontend Builder**: Compiles the frontend application using the NX build command.
21. - **Frontend**: Uses Nginx to serve the frontend static files.
22. - **Backend**: Sets up the backend service, ready to connect to the MongoDB database.
23.
24. ## [default.conf](default.conf)
25.
26. The `default.conf` file is the Nginx configuration for the frontend service. It
27. sets up the server to listen on port 80 and serve files from
28. the `/usr/share/nginx/html/web-editor` directory, with a fallback to
29. `index.html` for single-page application routing.
30.
31. ## [docker-compose.yml](docker-compose.yml)
32.
33. The `docker-compose.yml` file is used for local development. It defines two
34. services:
35.
36. - **mongo**: The MongoDB database service.
37. - **mongo-express**: A web-based MongoDB administration interface.
38.
39. ## [stack.yml](stack.yml)
```

```

40.
41. The `stack.yml` file is used for deploying the application stack to a Docker
42. Swarm cluster. It includes service definitions for the frontend, backend,
43. MongoDB, and Mongo Express, along with their respective configurations for
44. Traefik labels, networks, and secrets.
45.
46. ## Usage
47.
48. To build and run the services locally, you can use Docker Compose:
49.
50. ```shell
51. docker-compose -f docker-compose.yml up --build
52. ```
53.
54. For deployment to a Docker Swarm cluster, first ensure that the `traefik-public`
55. network is created and then deploy the stack:
56.
57. ```shell
58. docker stack deploy -c stack.yml openpra
59. ```

```

The following code snippets contain the contents of *docker-compose.yml* file:

```

1. version: '3.6'
2.
3. volumes:
4.   data_db:
5.
6. services:
7.   mongo:
8.     image: mongo:latest
9.     ports:
10.      - '27017:27017'
11.     volumes:
12.      - data_db:/data/db
13.   mongo-express:
14.     image: mongo-express
15.     restart: always
16.     ports:
17.      - '8081:8081'
18.     environment:
19.      - ME_CONFIG_MONGODB_SERVER=mongo

```

The following code snippets contain the contents of *stack.yml* file, which is responsible for setting project specific configurations:

```

1. version: '3.3'
2.
3. networks:
4.   db_net:
5.     driver: overlay
6.     attachable: true
7.   backend:

```

```

 8.   driver: overlay
 9.   attachable: true
10.  traefik-public:
11.   external: true
12.
13. secrets:
14.   CI_JWT_SECRET_KEY:
15.     file: secrets/DSF_JWT_SECRET_KEY.secret
16.
17. services:
18.   frontend:
19.     image: ${IMAGE_FRONTEND}
20.     networks:
21.       - traefik-public
22.       - backend
23.     volumes:
24.       - "/etc/localtime:/etc/localtime:ro"
25.       - "/etc/timezone:/etc/timezone:ro"
26.   deploy:
27.     labels:
28.       - traefik.enable=true
29.       - traefik.docker.network=traefik-public
30.       - traefik.constraint-label=traefik-public
31.       - traefik.http.routers.${APP_NAME}-frontend-http.rule=Host(`${HOST_URL?Variable not
set}`)
32.       - traefik.http.routers.${APP_NAME}-frontend-http.entrypoints=http
33.       - traefik.http.routers.${APP_NAME}-frontend-http.middlewares=https-redirect,gzip
34.       - traefik.http.routers.${APP_NAME}-frontend-http.service=${APP_NAME}-frontend
35.       - traefik.http.routers.${APP_NAME}-frontend-https.rule=Host(`${HOST_URL?Variable not
set}`)
36.       - traefik.http.routers.${APP_NAME}-frontend-https.entrypoints=https
37.       - traefik.http.routers.${APP_NAME}-frontend-https.tls=true
38.       - traefik.http.routers.${APP_NAME}-frontend-https.tls.certresolver=le
39.       - traefik.http.routers.${APP_NAME}-frontend-https.middlewares=gzip
40.       - traefik.http.routers.${APP_NAME}-frontend-https.service=${APP_NAME}-frontend
41.       - traefik.http.services.${APP_NAME}-frontend.loadbalancer.server.port=80
42.
43.   backend:
44.     image: ${IMAGE_BACKEND}
45.     networks:
46.       - traefik-public
47.       - backend
48.       - db_net
49.     secrets:
50.       - CI_JWT_SECRET_KEY
51.     environment:
52.       MONGO_URL: mongodb://mongodb:27017
53.       JWT_SECRET_KEY: /run/secrets/CI_JWT_SECRET_KEY
54.       SENTRY_DSN: ${CI_SENTRY_DSN}
55.       SENTRY_ENV: ${CI_SENTRY_ENV}
56.       DEBUG: ${CI_DEBUG}
57.       DEPLOYMENT: 'true'
58.     depends_on:
59.       - mongodb
60.     volumes:

```

```

61.     - "/etc/localtime:/etc/localtime:ro"
62.     - "/etc/timezone:/etc/timezone:ro"
63.     deploy:
64.       labels:
65.         - traefik.enable=true
66.         - traefik.docker.network=traefik-public
67.         - traefik.constraint-label=traefik-public
68.         - traefik.http.routers.${APP_NAME}-backend-http.rule=Host(`${HOST_URL?Variable not set}`)
&& PathPrefix(`/api`)
69.         - traefik.http.routers.${APP_NAME}-backend-http.entrypoints=http
70.         - traefik.http.routers.${APP_NAME}-backend-http.middlewares=https-redirect,gzip
71.         - traefik.http.routers.${APP_NAME}-backend-http.service=${APP_NAME}-backend
72.         - traefik.http.routers.${APP_NAME}-backend-https.rule=Host(`${HOST_URL?Variable not
set}`) && PathPrefix(`/api`)
73.         - traefik.http.routers.${APP_NAME}-backend-https.entrypoints=https
74.         - traefik.http.routers.${APP_NAME}-backend-https.tls=true
75.         - traefik.http.routers.${APP_NAME}-backend-https.tls.certresolver=le
76.         - traefik.http.routers.${APP_NAME}-backend-https.middlewares=gzip
77.         - traefik.http.routers.${APP_NAME}-backend-https.service=${APP_NAME}-backend
78.         - traefik.http.services.${APP_NAME}-backend.loadbalancer.server.port=8000
79.
80.     mongodb-express:
81.       image: mongo-express:latest
82.       networks:
83.         - traefik-public
84.         - db_net
85.       volumes:
86.         - "/etc/localtime:/etc/localtime:ro"
87.         - "/etc/timezone:/etc/timezone:ro"
88.       environment:
89.         ME_CONFIG_MONGODB_SERVER: mongodb
90.         ME_CONFIG_MONGODB_ENABLE_ADMIN: 'true'
91.         ME_CONFIG_SITE_BASEURL: /mongo/
92.       depends_on:
93.         - mongodb
94.       deploy:
95.         labels:
96.           - traefik.enable=true
97.           - traefik.docker.network=traefik-public
98.           - traefik.constraint-label=traefik-public
99.           - traefik.http.routers.${APP_NAME}-express-http.rule=Host(`${HOST_URL?Variable not set}`)
&& PathPrefix(`/mongo`)
100.          - traefik.http.routers.${APP_NAME}-express-http.entrypoints=http
101.          - traefik.http.routers.${APP_NAME}-express-http.middlewares=https-redirect,gzip
102.          - traefik.http.routers.${APP_NAME}-express-http.service=${APP_NAME}-express
103.          - traefik.http.routers.${APP_NAME}-express-https.rule=Host(`${HOST_URL?Variable not
set}`) && PathPrefix(`/mongo`)
104.          - traefik.http.routers.${APP_NAME}-express-https.entrypoints=https
105.          - traefik.http.routers.${APP_NAME}-express-https.tls=true
106.          - traefik.http.routers.${APP_NAME}-express-https.tls.certresolver=le
107.          - traefik.http.routers.${APP_NAME}-express-https.middlewares=gzip
108.          - traefik.http.routers.${APP_NAME}-express-https.service=${APP_NAME}-express
109.          - traefik.http.services.${APP_NAME}-express.loadbalancer.server.port=8081
110.
111.     mongodb:

```

```

112.     image: mongo:latest
113.     networks:
114.         - db_net
115.     volumes:
116.         - "$ENV_SHARED_VOLUME_PATH/mongodb:/data/db"
117.         - "/etc/localtime:/etc/localtime:ro"
118.         - "/etc/timezone:/etc/timezone:ro"

```

The following code snippets contain the contents of *godana.dockerfile* and *godana-entripoint.sh*. Both files are responsible for enforcing automated static code checking to ensure the quality of the code:

```

1. ### godana.dockerfile
2.
3. FROM jetbrains/qodana-js:latest as BASE
4.
5. ENV DEBIAN_FRONTEND=noninteractive
6. ENV NX_VERSION=17.1.2
7. ENV BUILD_PACKAGES \
8.     make cmake g++ python3
9.
10. ENV SCRAM_BUILD_PACKAGES \
11.     libxml2-dev libomp-dev \
12.     libgoogle-perftools-dev libboost-program-options-dev \
13.     libboost-math-dev libboost-random-dev libboost-filesystem-dev \
14.     libboost-test-dev libboost-date-time-dev libjemalloc-dev
15.
16. ENV SCRAM_RUNTIME_PACKAGES \
17.     libxml2 libboost-filesystem1.74.0 libboost-program-options1.74.0 \
18.     libtcmalloc-minimal4 libjemalloc2
19.
20. SHELL ["/bin/bash", "-c"]
21. RUN --mount=target=/var/lib/apt/lists,type=cache,sharing=locked \
22.     --mount=target=/var/cache/apt,type=cache,sharing=locked \
23.     rm -f /etc/apt/apt.conf.d/docker-clean && \
24.     apt update && \
25.     apt install -y --no-install-recommends $BUILD_PACKAGES $SCRAM_BUILD_PACKAGES
26.     $SCRAM_RUNTIME_PACKAGES && \
27.     npm install --global nx@$NX_VERSION
28. WORKDIR /data/project
29. COPY .. .
30.
31. RUN SHELL=bash pnpm setup && \
32.     source /root/.bashrc && \
33.     pnpm install
34.
35. COPY ../docker/qodana-entripoint.sh /docker-entripoint.d/
36. RUN chmod +x /docker-entripoint.d/qodana-entripoint.sh
37. ENTPRINT ["/bin/bash", "/docker-entripoint.d/qodana-entripoint.sh"]

```

```

1. #!/bin/bash
2. ### qodana-entrypoint.sh
3.
4. QODANA_DEFAULT_COVERAGE_DIR=".qodana/code-coverage"
5. SOURCE_DIR=/data/project
6. mkdir -p $SOURCE_DIR && cd $SOURCE_DIR
7.
8. # Check if $1 is empty, if so, set PROJECT_DIR to ".", otherwise use the value of $1
9. PROJECT_DIR="${1:-.}"
10.
11. # If PROJECT_DIR is ".", set PACKAGE_NAME to empty, otherwise replace all `/\` with `-\` in
PROJECT_DIR
12. if [ "$PROJECT_DIR" == "." ]; then
13.     PACKAGE_NAME=""
14.     COVERAGE_DIR="$QODANA_DEFAULT_COVERAGE_DIR"
15.     TEST_COMMAND="nx run-many -t test --coverage --coverageDirectory=$COVERAGE_DIR --
coverageReporters=lcovonly"
16.     MONOREPO="true"
17. else
18.     PACKAGE_NAME="${PROJECT_DIR//\//-}"
19.     PROJECT_DIR="packages/$PROJECT_DIR"
20.     COVERAGE_DIR="$PROJECT_DIR/$QODANA_DEFAULT_COVERAGE_DIR"
21.     TEST_COMMAND="nx test $PACKAGE_NAME --coverage --coverageDirectory=$COVERAGE_DIR --
coverageReporters=lcovonly"
22.     MONOREPO="false"
23. fi
24.
25. echo "with PACKAGE_NAME=$PACKAGE_NAME"
26. echo "with PROJECT_DIR=$PROJECT_DIR"
27. echo "with COVERAGE_DIR=$COVERAGE_DIR"
28. echo "with TEST_COMMAND=$TEST_COMMAND"
29.
30. # Function to always run qodana at the end
31. function post_test_fixes {
32.     if [ "$MONOREPO" == "true" ]; then
33.         echo "no fixes to run"
34.     else
35.         echo "running fixes"
36.         mkdir -p "$PROJECT_DIR/$PROJECT_DIR"
37.         cp -r "$PROJECT_DIR"/* "$PROJECT_DIR/$PROJECT_DIR/" || true
38.     fi
39. }
40.
41. # Function to always run qodana at the end
42. function finish {
43.     qodana --coverage-dir "$SOURCE_DIR/$COVERAGE_DIR" --project-dir "$SOURCE_DIR/$PROJECT_DIR"
44. }
45. trap finish EXIT
46.
47. # Execute the test command for the given coverage directory passed to the script
48. ${TEST_COMMAND}
49. post_test_fixes

```